

BROMINATION OF COMPOUNDS CONTAINING TWO AROMATIC NUCLEI. PART III. BROMINATION OF ARYL ESTERS OF *O*-CRESOTIC ACID

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Bromination of phenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-cresyl, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenyl and β -naphthyl esters of *o*-cresotic acid is described. In the case of phenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-cresyl esters mono- and dibromo derivatives are obtained. Their constitutions have been proved by hydrolysis and confirmed by synthesis.

The work is the extension of the work of Jadhav and Rangwala (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 89 ; *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 1, 616). It has been observed that the presence of the free OH group in the molecule facilitates the reaction and directs the bromine atom in the nucleus containing it, in the position *para* to the OH group. The presence of the negative group like NO₂ in the phenolic part further facilitates the reaction and brominated products separate out sooner. Phenyl, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-cresyl, *m*-(*p*-nitro)-phenyl and β -naphthyl esters have been worked out.

No higher bromo derivatives could be obtained by carrying out bromination in a solvent, but liquid bromine could give dibromo derivatives only in the case of phenyl and *m*-cresyl esters, whereas the dibromo derivatives of *o*- and *p*-cresyl esters could be prepared only by using their monobromo derivatives and liquid bromine.

The presence of NO₂ group in the nitrophenyl esters so completely deactivates the molecule that even with liquid bromine only monobromo compounds are obtained. In the case of β -naphthyl ester, a mixture of bromo compounds is formed which can not be completely purified.

The constitution of these bromo compounds has been proved by their hydrolysis and confirmed by their synthesis except in the case of the dibromo derivative of *p*-cresyl ester which has not been prepared.

EXPERIMENTAL

For the preparation of the monobromo derivatives 16 c.c. of a 20% solution of bromine in acetic acid for 4 g. of the acid were used at room temperature when bromine was readily absorbed and the bromo derivative separated in a crystalline form after about $\frac{1}{2}$ -1 hour, the ester being first dissolved in acetic acid. They are described in Table IA.

In the preparation of the dibromo derivatives of phenyl and *m*-cresyl esters, the ester and liquid bromine in the proportion of 1:2 by weight were used. Whilst in the case of *o*- and *p*-cresyl esters the monobromo compound and liquid bromine in the proportion of 2:1 and 1:1 respectively were used. In each case the reaction mixture was shaken for about half an hour and then diluted with water and treated with sodium bisulphite to remove the excess of bromine. They were crystallised from acetic acid. (*vide* Table IIA).

The hydrolysis of all the compounds described here was effected by boiling the substance under reflux with 5-8% sodium hydroxide solution for four to five hours and then passing carbon dioxide into the solution, when the phenolic portion separated. This

was removed by extraction with ether and the aqueous layer gave on acidification 5-bromo-*o*-cresotic acid. In the case of nitrophenols, β -naphthol and *p*-bromo-*o*-cresol and *p*-bromo-*m*-cresol, the phenols also were identified.

The synthesis of the bromo compounds has been carried out by using the quantities of the bromo-acid, required phenol and phosphorus oxychloride as shown in Tables IA and IIB and heating the reaction mixture at the temperatures shown, for about half an hour. The reaction mixture is then diluted with water and the solid washed with dilute alkali. It is finally crystallised from acetic acid and mixed melting point taken.

TABLE IA

TABLE IB

B.B. indicates bromobenzoate

Substance.	Formula.	M.p.	Found :	Calc.	Acid.	Phenol.	POCl ₃ .	Temp.
Phenyl 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-BB	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ Br	81-82°	Br. 26.3%	Br. 26.06%	2 g.	1.5 g.	1 c.c.	120-25°
<i>o</i> -Cresyl 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-BB	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₃ Br	147-48°	25.0	24.9	2	1.5	1	130-35°
<i>m</i> -Cresyl 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-BB	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₃ Br	124-26°	24.7	24.9	2	1.5	1	120-25°
<i>p</i> -Cresyl 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-BB	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₃ Br	123-24°	25.0	24.9	2	1.5	1	120-25°
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-BB	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₅ Br	133-34°	23.0	22.7	2	1.5	1	125-30°
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-BB	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₅ NBr	187-88°	22.7 N, 3.9	22.7 N, 3.98	4	3.5	2.5	130-35°
β -Naphthyl 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-BB	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₃ Br	66°	Br. 22.3	Br. 22.4	4	3	2.5	130-35°

TABLE IIA

TABLE IIB

4-Bromo phenyl 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-BB	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₃ Br ₂	147-48°	Br. 41.2	Br. 41.4	5 g.	4 g.	3 c.c.	130-35°
2-Methyl-4-bromo-phenyl 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-BB	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃ Br ₂	150-51°	39.8	40.0	2	1.5	1	130-35°
3-Methyl-4-bromophenyl-2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-BB	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃ Br ₂	138-39°	40.1	40.0	4	3.5	2.5	125-30°
4-Methyl-2-bromo-phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-BB	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃ Br ₂	92-93°	39.8	40.0				

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